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The Trust in Industry in Europe

Between March and December 2022, he decreased on average of -868.16%

The Eurostat calculates the value of the indicator of industrial trust in Europe. This indicator is built through the analysis of questionnaires in which the industrialists are asked of applications relating to production expectations, orders and supplies of finished products that are considered negatively. The data are decreased. The data is produced by the European Commission with monthly deadline. In the following analysis the data between March and December 2022 were analyzed.

Ranking of countries by value of industrial trust in December 2022. Ireland and Montenegro are in the first place for the value of the indicator of industrial trust, with a value equal to 9.8 units, followed by Albania with a value of 9.1 unit and Croatia with a value of 8.4 units. In the middle of the standings there are Slovenia with a value equal to -3.4 units, followed by Hungary with a value equal to -3.8 units and Spain with a value equal to -4.8 units. Lithuania closes the ranking with a value equal to -17.3 units, followed by Poland with a value equal to -19.7 units and from Malta with a value equal to -23.5 units.

Ranking of countries by the percentage variation of the indicator of industrial trust between 03/2022 and 12/2022. Albania is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the industrial trust indicator between 03/2022 and 12/2022 with a value of 168% equal to 6 units, followed by Montenegro with a value of 165% equal to 6 units and from Croatia with a value of +1%. In the middle of the standings there are Slovenia with a value equal to -192% equal to -7 unit, followed by Cyprus with a value of -205% and Turkey with a value equal to -211%. They close the Malta ranking with a value equal to -1.779%, followed by Hungary with a value equal to -2,000 units and by Denmark with a value equal to -16.700%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. In particular, the following Clusters are identified or:

- Cluster 1: Austria, Slovakia, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Northern Macedonia, Czech Republic, Portugal, Serbia, Bulgaria, Italy, Greece, Romania, Spain, Hungary, Slovenia, France, Turkey;
- Cluster 2: Poland, Malta, Belgium, Cyprus, Denmark, Luxembourg;
- Cluster 3: Germany, Sweden, Croatia, Ireland, Albania, Montenegro, Finland, Netherlands.

Considering the value of the Clusters median, the following order is: C3 = 7.75 > C1 = -4.3 > C2 = -16.1. From a geographical point of view, it appears that the countries of Northern Europe and Scandinavia are at the highest levels in terms of indicator of industrial trust.

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Network Analysis with Manhattan's distance. Below is an analysis with the Network Analysis with Manhattan's distance. A single complex network structure is detected as indicated below or:

- Bulgaria has a connection with Serbia for a value of 0.61;
- Serbia has a connection with Bulgaria for a value of 0.61 units and with Romania equal to a value of 0.58 units;
- Romania has a connection with Serbia for a value of 0.58 units and with Turkey for a value of 0.7 units;
- Turkey has a connection with Romania equal to a value of 0.7 units, with Italy for a value of 0.65 units, with Slovenia for a value of 0.68 units and with Spain for a value of 0.67 units;
- Italy has a connection with Turkey for a value of 0.65 units and with Greece for a value of 0.63 units;
- Greece has a connection with Italy for a value of 0.63 units and with Slovenia equal to a value of 0.69 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Turkey has a connection for a value of 0.68 units and with Greece for a value of 0.69 units;
- Spain has a connection with Turkey for a value of 0.67 units and with France equal to a value of 0.56 units;
- France has a connection with Turkey for a value equal to 0.72 units and with Spain for a value of 0.56 units, with Hungary for a value of 0.57 units, with Portugal equal to a value of 0.69 units and with Latvia for a value equal to 0.71 units;
- Hungary has a connection with France for a value of 0.57 units;
- Portugal has a connection with France equal to a value of 0.69 units, with Lithuania for a value of 0.6 units and with Latvia for a value of 0.46 units;
- Latvia has a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.46 units and with France for a value of 0.71 units and with Lithuania for a value of 0.39 units;
- Lithuania has a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.6 units and with Latvia for a value of 0.39 units.

Network Analysis is useful for identifying the propagation effects of the modifications of the industrial trusted index. For example, if the industrial trusted index increases (or decreases) in France by a unit then increases (or decreases) by 0.57 in Hungary, increases (or decreases) by 0.69 in Portugal, increases (or decreases) 0.71 in Latvia, increases (or decreases) by 0.56 in Spain. Obviously, these relationships must not be understood as cause-effect relationships, as regards the contrary as the connection existing in the structure of the historical series of data.

Conclusions. In summary we can say that the value of industrial trust has decreased in almost all the countries between March 2022 and December 2022. This reduction is evident in almost all countries except for Albania with +168%, Montenegro +165% and Croatia +1 %. In all other countries considered the variation of the indicator of industrial trust is negative. This negative trend can be easily understood because of the worsening of the macroeconomic condition due to the mix of post-covid, inflation, energy crisis, Sino-American tension, and Russian-Ukraine war. The set of these elements has certainly worsened the structure of supply chains worldwide creating uncertainty in industry. Obviously, this uncertainty finds its maximum manifestation also in the reduction of consumer trust. It follows that companies could soon start producing less because of the growing costs of energy and raw materials on the one hand and on the other side for the contraction of domestic and international demand. A condition that, net of each cassandra syndrome, could glimpse the approach of the crisis also from the side of the production.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Indicatore della Fiducia Industriale										
Country	2022-03	2022-04	2022-05	2022-06	2022-07	2022-08	2022-09	2022-10	2022-11	2022-12
Ireland	★ 11,4	★ 10,7	★ 5,6	★ 17	★ 1,4	★ 7	★ 8,9	★ 6,6	★ 3,5	★ 9,8
Montenegro	★ 3,7	★ 8,3	★ 1,6	★ 4,4	★ 22,9	★ -2,7	★ -1,4	★ 5	★ 1,9	★ 9,8
Albania	★ 3,4	★ 2,6	★ 6,3	★ 8,8	★ 9,6	★ 12,4	★ 9	★ 6,8	★ 7,2	★ 9,1
Croatia	★ 8,3	★ 10,1	★ 10,7	★ 12,3	★ 3,7	★ 2,8	★ 5,1	★ 8,4	★ 6,2	★ 8,4
Sweden	★ 29,3	★ 23,8	★ 27,3	★ 20,5	★ 21,5	★ 19,8	★ 11,9	★ 7,7	★ 8,5	★ 7,1
Germany	★ 16,1	★ 16,1	★ 14,9	★ 15	★ 11	★ 7,6	★ 4,2	★ 3	★ 3,1	★ 2,7
Serbia	★ -4	★ -0,8	★ -2,2	★ 0,9	★ 2,6	★ 1	★ -0,5	★ -1,1	★ 0,7	★ 1,6
Netherlands	★ 6,5	★ 7,5	★ 6,3	★ 5	★ 4,8	★ 2,1	★ 0,4	★ -0,1	★ 0,8	★ 1
Bulgaria	★ -5,9	★ -3,8	★ -4,9	★ -0,9	★ -1,1	★ -1,7	★ -1,6	★ -2	★ -0,4	★ 0,7
North Macedonia	★ -6,2	★ -1,1	★ -4,2	★ -5,5	★ -6,2	★ -1,3	★ -2,2	★ -7,2	★ -0,7	★ 0,3
Greece	★ 9,6	★ 3	★ 5,1	★ 0,1	★ -0,1	★ -1,8	★ -5,1	★ -6,9	★ -5,1	★ -0,1
Romania	★ -0,1	★ 0,9	★ 0	★ -0,5	★ -0,8	★ -1,4	★ -1	★ 0,1	★ -0,3	★ -1
Türkiye	★ 2,8	★ 1,4	★ 0,2	★ -1	★ -3,4	★ -1,7	★ -5,3	★ -3,7	★ -3,1	★ -3,1
Italy	★ 4,4	★ 4,3	★ 3,7	★ 2,5	★ 0,7	★ -1,2	★ -3,6	★ -4,1	★ -3	★ -3,4
Slovenia	★ 3,7	★ 4,5	★ 1,8	★ -0,3	★ -1,3	★ -1,5	★ -7,9	★ -9	★ -4,6	★ -3,4
Hungary	★ 0,2	★ -0,4	★ 1,2	★ 3,4	★ 0,2	★ -2,2	★ -3	★ -7,6	★ -9,9	★ -3,8
Spain	★ 4,3	★ -1,4	★ 1	★ 1,7	★ -4,9	★ -5,5	★ -5,2	★ -3,9	★ -7,6	★ -4,8
Portugal	★ -3,8	★ -1,3	★ -3,8	★ -3,3	★ -4,1	★ -5,6	★ -5,7	★ -7	★ -7,2	★ -6,6
Finland	★ 15,6	★ 14,3	★ 12,7	★ 8,7	★ 4,7	★ 1,5	★ -1,1	★ -4,7	★ -8,1	★ -7,6
Cyprus	★ -8	★ -9,4	★ -10,5	★ -13	★ -7,4	★ -7,5	★ -4,1	★ -6,6	★ -9,8	★ -8,4
Czechia	★ -4,2	★ -1,8	★ 4,1	★ 2,9	★ -3,8	★ -5,2	★ -4,4	★ -11	★ -12,7	★ -8,5
Latvia	★ -1,9	★ -3,5	★ -2,8	★ -4,5	★ -4	★ -5,5	★ -8,1	★ -8,8	★ -9,4	★ -8,8
Austria	★ 11,4	★ 9,4	★ 3,3	★ 6,6	★ 2,8	★ -3,7	★ -3,6	★ -6,7	★ -7,4	★ -8,9
France	★ 1,4	★ -0,4	★ -0,1	★ 0	★ -0,8	★ -4,7	★ -6,6	★ -6,8	★ -8,5	★ -9,4
Slovakia	★ 3,5	★ -3,9	★ 3,6	★ -4,2	★ -5,5	★ -7,6	★ -7,3	★ -9,6	★ -12,8	★ -13,1
Belgium	★ -5,7	★ -1,6	★ -3,4	★ -8,2	★ -7	★ -10,6	★ -16,7	★ -20	★ -18,8	★ -13,7
Estonia	★ 11,5	★ 10,5	★ 8,8	★ 4,4	★ -1,8	★ -6,4	★ -9,2	★ -11,3	★ -13,3	★ -14,4
Luxembourg	★ -2,6	★ 0,8	★ -1,9	★ -1,2	★ -12,5	★ -9,7	★ -4,6	★ -13,5	★ -17,8	★ -15,6
Denmark	★ -0,1	★ 3,5	★ -3,5	★ -8,6	★ -9,7	★ -2,9	★ -10,2	★ -15,7	★ -14,6	★ -16,6
Lithuania	★ -3,3	★ -1,5	★ -0,6	★ -4,4	★ -2,9	★ -5,3	★ -7,4	★ -11	★ -10,6	★ -17,3
Poland	★ -16	★ -15,2	★ -15,7	★ -17,4	★ -19,9	★ -20,2	★ -21,7	★ -21,1	★ -21,2	★ -19,7
Malta	★ 1,4	★ -2,2	★ -14,8	★ -10,3	★ -14,3	★ -21,4	★ -11,4	★ -20,9	★ -16,7	★ -23,5

